

NEED OF HUMAN RIGHTS AWARENESS AMONG DISADVANTAGED SECTIONS FOR NATION BUILDING

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Abstract

This paper attempts to understand the need of human rights awareness for the disadvantaged sections of nation and their contribution for nation building. As in case of disadvantaged sections of the society the opportunities are bleak and social-financial conditions are not favorable with this section of the society and in the field of educational access and equity they are lagging far behind than the main strata's of the society. The Disadvantaged groups are those that belong to the SC, ST, socially and educationally backward class or such other group having disadvantage owing to social, cultural, economical, geographical, linguistic, gender, or such other factor as may be specified by the appropriate Government by notification. It is over two decades since India has ratified and effectively endeavored to implement the United Nations Convention on the Human Rights and concurrently enacted significant legislations and policies to reinforce the country's response in mainstreaming rights of disadvantaged sections. It is imperative that

this immense human potential be given an enabled environment, empowered and effectively mobilized for the development of future nation. This paper emphasized for creating awareness of human rights among disadvantaged sections and to develop evidence-based policies for the growth of this section so that they can contribute in the nation building.

Key words: *Human Rights, Disadvantaged Sections, Awareness, Nation Building*

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INTRODUCTION

The Human Rights Education of Vulnerable and Disadvantaged Groups has aim to work towards the realization of rights guaranteed legally and fulfill the objective of the United Nations, and international law of human rights to provide a stable and peaceful life to every individual, without any kind of discrimination. To achieve these objectives, nation-states have adopted a number of legal texts and evolved specific policies to help discriminated groups realize and enjoy legally guaranteed basic minimum rights at the international and national level.

Human Rights have never shown any kind of discrimination towards any individual or group of people. They apply equally to any country or culture without any bias on grounds of sex, race, religion, caste or community and language. They only advocate the welfare and well-being of all persons with equal treatment everywhere at all times. However, the socio-economic, political and cultural diversities, prevailing in each state across the world, and politics of the nation states, deprive the free exercise of human rights to a certain number of people. Any type of deprivation, which has a direct bearing on the right to life and dignity of people, certainly deprives them of the

enjoyment of their guaranteed human rights. Such deprived people are normally referred to as vulnerable and disadvantaged communities or groups.

To wipe out the miseries of these people, and to help them to achieve the equal status with that of the developed sections of a society, it is the responsibility of both nation-states and individuals to extend a helping hand to the extent possible to uplift them in realizing their rights.

However, the political, social, economic and cultural inequalities present in each society many a times, hamper the rights of the weaker sections of a society, thereby obstructing them from fully realizing their rights. In spite of clearly articulating the parameters of equality and non-discrimination on any count, discrimination based on gender, race, language, and other counts still prevail in various societies around the World. Taking into consideration various prevailing circumstances, the international community extended concessions to the disadvantaged groups across the world, not only to remove the apparent deficiencies in the realization of their legally guaranteed human rights, but also

to make them self-sufficient in exercise of their rights on an equal footing.

HUMAN RIGHTS IN INDIAN CONTEXT

In the Indian context, the Constitution of India guaranteed to all the people of India the civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights for their realization by all sections of the polity without any kind of discrimination. However, due to poverty, customary and cultural practices prevalent in the country, equal opportunity has been denied to various groups of people. This has prevented them from enjoying their rights equally on par with other developed sections of the society. There are various disadvantaged groups of people such as women, children, Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, Linguistic Minorities, Religious Minorities, Sexual Minorities etc. In order to augment their rights, the Constitution of India has provided a number of concessions to protect them from exploitation by other groups. However, from a variety of discriminatory practices that are prevalent against the above groups, it has become apparent that the existing environment for the free exercise of rights is in some way deficient. In order to bridge the gaps in the social system, the

Legislature has adopted a number of progressive legislations extending concessions to augment the rights of these people. The Judiciary too in a number of cases has liberally interpreted the provisions of the Constitution and various legislations to uphold the rights of the vulnerable groups. The expansion of Public Interest Litigation or Social Action Litigation by the Supreme Court of India is a welcome feature, compared to its counterparts across the world, to augment the rights of discriminated groups.

Education is a vital tool in Indian Society; a society that is growing economically and continues to struggle for social justice. Therefore, the aim of the Indian government is to equip its Universities and school students to understand and spread the message of human rights. This will help to evolve effective solutions to wipe out the tears from every eye of the millions of people whose rights are adversely affected, and who do not have at their disposal adequate knowledge and tools for the realization of their legally guaranteed rights. Apart from the above, equipping the younger generations with Human Rights knowledge would indeed, strengthen the justice delivery system in a more coherent manner.

Meaning of Vulnerable groups

The meaning of vulnerable is highly evasive. However, in common understanding, people who are easily susceptible to physical or emotional injury, or subject to unnecessary criticism, or in a less advantageous position in any society may be defined as vulnerable people.

Accordingly, vulnerable groups are those groups of people who may find it difficult to lead a comfortable life, and lack developmental opportunities due to their disadvantageous position.

Further, due to adverse socio-economical, cultural, and other practices present in each society, they find it difficult many a times to exercise their human rights fully. In the language of human rights vulnerable groups may be defined as, certain groups of population who often encounter discriminatory treatment, or need some kind of special attention for protection of the State to avoid exploitation or from a harmful environment.

Meaning of Disadvantaged Groups

According to the general perspective of International Law of Human Rights, disadvantaged groups are the people who are denied free access to the guaranteed rights.

People who are discriminated based on sex, race, by birth in a particular community, religious or disability or any other criteria that is specific to each society may generally described as disadvantaged people.

Based on the socio, economic, cultural perspectives, the classification of these groups vary from country to country. In general, women, children, socially, economically, culturally deprived sections, disabled, minorities etc. form part of disadvantaged groups. Poverty is the main contributing factor towards degradation of the status of these people that are classified as disadvantaged groups (Steven, 2003).

The above definitions are only illustrative in nature. Despite the commitment of international law of human rights towards the promotion and protection of rights of these groups, there is no agreed standard definition, concept, or standard classification of list of people who are to be classified as vulnerable and disadvantaged groups.

Concept of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups

Human rights place duties on the individuals, and states to eradicate all

types of discriminatory practices that are adopted towards those people who are weak, oppressed on any count. However, due to poverty and other social, cultural barricades that exist in each society, there are millions of people not able to enjoy their basic rights, equally with that of progressive sections. Apart from the individual, social, and customary practices followed in each society, the politics and policies of nation-states also contribute largely, for the vulnerability of large number of people around the World.

In view of the existence of large number of vulnerable and disadvantaged people, International Law of Human Rights extends special considerations for the promotion and protection of their rights and works towards eradication of discriminations. Accordingly, the United Nations has adopted a number of Declarations, Conventions, and Covenants to uplift the rights of these people. It also established special commissions and organizations to deal with the rights of such people whose rights are at jeopardy.

Due to lack of an acceptable definition, many a times, the UN bodies work on ad-hoc basis to augment the rights of disadvantaged people. The United Nations

and its other bodies including the Human Rights Council regularly adopt a number of guidelines for implementation by the states in their efforts to curb the threats against the disadvantaged people.

Disadvantaged and Vulnerable Peoples

Women and Girls: Women and girls are normally in a disadvantaged position all over the World. However, compared to developed countries, they are in a more disadvantageous position in developing countries due to abject poverty, other social, cultural, and derogatory customary practices adopted in each country.

Children: Children again are the most disadvantaged people in the World. Children of developing countries, compared to developed countries face a number of problems, such as poverty, malnutrition, and other socio, economic, cultural abuses.

Disabled Persons: Disability assumes different meaning in different contexts. However, according to UN Declaration on the Rights of Disabled Persons (1975) "any person unable to ensure by himself or herself, wholly or partly the necessities of a normal individual and or social life as a result of a deficiency either congenital or not in his /her physical or mental abilities" could

be described as disabled. Accordingly, any individual may also qualify as disabled if he/she has had impairment in the past or is seen as disabled based on a personal or group standard, or norm. Such impairments may include physical, sensory, and cognitive or developmental disabilities. People who suffer from mental disorders such as, psychiatric or psychological infirmities are also described as disabled persons. The United Nations considering the increasing number of disabled people, and to augment their rights adopted a convention in 2006. It has also established an organ called as UN Enable, which takes care of the interests of these people. In the Millennium goals, the UN adopted a specific goal to protect the rights of the Disabled.

In the National sphere to uphold the dignity and freedom of the disabled the Union and the States adopted a number of legislative and policy formulations. To protect their dignity and to remove the stigma of disabled from the minds of these people, the Union and State Governments took a number of steps including extending 3% reservation in education and jobs. Further, the Government to provide a social status to these people named them as differently able people.

Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes:

According to Article 341 of the Constitution, Scheduled Castes are such castes, races, tribes, or groups within such castes, races, or tribes, which have been declared as such by the President of India through a public notification for each state.

According to Article 342 of the Constitution, the Scheduled Tribes are such tribes or tribal communities, or groups within these tribes or tribal communities, which have been declared as such by the President through a public notification for each state.

All the groups stated above are of a general classification. However, it may vary from country to country and different classification is evolved many a times, which may not have a standard international criterion to define vulnerable group. In the Indian context, the following may be broadly classified as vulnerable groups of people based on socio-economic, cultural and other criteria. They are as follows: (1) women; (2) Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes; (3) Children; (4) Aged People; (5) Migrant workers; (6) Sex Workers and HIV /AIDS people; and (7) Sexual minorities.

General Framework to Eradicate Problems of the Vulnerable and Disadvantaged groups

All the documents of human rights are committed for the promotion of human rights of all, including the vulnerable groups. In order to promote and protect the rights of these people, the international community has adopted a number of special documents.

In order to enable the disadvantaged sections of people, the United Nations appointed a number of committees and commissions to deal with the issues specific to each vulnerable group. Based on the reports of the various committees, the UN has adopted a general framework to eradicate and to address the adverse situations faced by these groups. The suggestions include:

- equal pay for equal work;
- independent mechanism or commission to establish and to deal with each category of people;
- basic compulsory education;
- special concessions to these people;
- provisions to enable them to take part in the governance;

- independent forums to express their grievances;
- easy accessibility to medical and health care; and,
- efforts to raise the standard of living, subsidized food supply, eradicate malnutrition, abolish any customary practices that threaten their survival, over all social security etc.

In 2008 the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in order to cover more groups of people and to extend the purview of the problems afflicted to them has introduced the terminology marginalized and disadvantaged groups instead of Vulnerable groups.

The 2008 guidelines appealed to the states to provide specific data on the efforts of the states in raising the standards of these groups to enhance their rights. The guidelines include the training programmes, specific data on housing, right to food, education, scientific progression, malnutrition, health, and other social welfare schemes evolved from time to time by the states.

Based on the guidelines, each state was asked to submit independent reports for

the scrutiny of the United Nations. In this regard, the Government of India, submitted its report in 2008 and 2012, which clearly stated in detail the constitutional policy, the schemes adopted by the Union and states with respect to each group of the people of vulnerable or disadvantaged sections. The detailed programme list submitted by India was commended by many states for the steps taken by the country especially to uplift the rights of women, children, SC/ST's, backward class people, older persons, and disabled. A number of suggestions were rendered at the same time, to overcome the age-old practices that are still adopted against these people especially, women, SC/STs, minorities, and other backward classes in various parts of the country.

Though the UN is making the best efforts to eradicate the problems encountered by many of the disadvantaged people in the world, still resistance by many advanced countries to provide data and to initiate steps to eliminate the ills of disadvantaged people is far from satisfactory.

The dissemination of the objectives of human rights through education in large scale is the only way out, as highlighted by the UN, in its various policy formulations

and legal documents, to promote and protect the rights of these groups. In February 2012, the General Assembly of the United Nations through Resolution 66/137 reaffirmed that it is the duty of every individual and organ of the society to strive to teach and promote education to foster respect for Human Rights.

It has adopted a Plan of Action for the impartation of human rights education entitled as World Programme For Human Rights Education. It is the hope of the World body that such dissemination in turn will certainly equip the people, especially the marginalized groups, to know their rights, in order to attain just and favorable conditions for the augmentation of their rights as enshrined by the documents of international law of human rights.

Women's Rights

After independence, the Constitution of India adopted on January 26, 1950 abolished all kinds of discriminatory practices against women. The constitution on the lines of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 recognizing the rights of women has a number of provisions to protect in augmenting their rights. In spite of progressive legislations and judicial pronouncements, the misuse of

technology, rapid urbanization, poverty, natural calamities such as famines, floods etc., many a times worsens the situation of women in exercising their rights to the fullest extent as guaranteed by law. Indian women suffer a number of inequalities especially in the domestic front on the name of customary and religious faiths. This is more evident especially in issues relating to marriage, customary ceremonial functions, choice of reproductive rights, payment of wages, especially in the agricultural and other sectors, inheritance of property, domestic violence, custodial rapes, sexual harassment at work place and in society.

Apart from the above legislations, the government of India established the National Commission of Women to cater to the needs of women in a number of areas. The Indian Judiciary in a number of judgments has greatly contributed for the augmentation of women's rights in a wide array of areas.

The Government of India in the year 2001 adopted a National Policy of Women for advancement, development and empowerment of women. The Ministry of Women and child development takes care of various aspects of women's

development and empowerment. The aims and objectives of the policy are looked after by the Ministry to achieve self sufficiency of Indian women. The aims and objectives of the policy are:

- (I). Creating an environment through positive economic and social policies for full development of women to enable them to realize their full potential.
- (II). The de-jure and de-facto enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedom by women on equal basis with men in all spheres – political, economic, social, cultural and civil.
- (III). Equal access to participation and decision making of women in social, political, and economic life of the nation.
- (IV). Equal access to women to healthcare, quality education at all levels, career and vocational guidance, employment, equal remuneration, occupational health and safety, social security and public office etc.

- (V). Strengthening legal systems aimed at elimination of all forms of discrimination against women.
- (VI). Changing societal attitudes and community practices by active participation and involvement of both men and women.
- (VII). Mainstreaming a gender perspective in the development process.
- (VIII). Elimination of discrimination and all forms of violence against women and the girl child;
- (IX). Building and strengthening partnerships with civil society, particularly women's organizations.

Apart from National Policies and other initiatives, the Government of India and the State Governments has evolved a number of policy formulations, schemes through annual budgets for the promotion of women's rights.

In a traditional society like India, where many women goddess are worshipped with lot of devotion and respect, when it comes to equal treatment of their biological partners, both men and society keep them in low profile. Many a times they are

considered as servants of the home, and are looked at as sexual objects. Their economic capacity is deprived to make them dependent on the male dominated society. The traditional, economic, social and cultural disbeliefs and age old customary practices of intimidating cruel practices that are prevalent in many parts of the world has to be halted with welcome sign of considering them as partners in progress. Love, affection, care with utmost respect for the augmentation of their rights alone would result in uplifting their rights and strengthen the international and national efforts in realizing their rights as human beings.

Human Rights and Children

Among the various vulnerable groups, children are another major category, whose rights are affected by negligence and other conditions in every society. In many societies in the world, especially in the developing world from tender age, their rights are abused for a variety of reasons. A child has a number of basic rights, such as, protection and prevention of illegal abortion, right to nourishment, adequate nutritious food, basic health care, love and affection of family, society, not to abuse the tender age, recreation, right

to basic education, right to development, right to identity, community and social life, etc.

Poverty is a negation to the rights of millions of children in many societies around the world. Most often, they are pushed to work from the tender age at the cost of their physical, intellectual, and psychological development. According to the United Nations Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) around ten million children every year below the age of five die due to lack of proper medical care. About 100 million children mostly girls are not in schools. In the developing world, about 150 million children are underweight due to lack of nutritious food. Therefore, it is the duty of family, society and the nation-states to render their assistance to augment the rights of children in every sphere.

According to many reports of international agencies and non-governmental organizations, India is the major country compared to many of the under developed countries including the African region, where in the plight of children is worse in enjoying their rights as subjects of the State. The main reason is the inefficiency of the administrative wings of the state to properly implement and monitor

the situation, apart from poverty, which is another significant factor that deprives the rights of children.

In order to augment the rights of children, in a number of cases, the Indian Judiciary has expanded the rights of children by interpreting provisions of the Constitution, various statutes and International Human Rights instruments to which India is a party highlighting the increasing role of state in the protection and promotion of rights of children in the following areas.

- Prevention of mental and physical torture
- Prevention of Child Sexual Abuse and Trafficking
- Prevention of Illegal Adoptions by foster parents
- Prevention of Child Labour in hazardous industries
- Rehabilitation of girls found in prostitution and trafficking
- Right to Compulsory Education of Children
- Providing rehabilitation to children of prostitutes

- Providing facilities to children in Juvenile Homes and keeping of Child offenders in Juvenile Homes
- Stream lining of mid-day meal scheme with nutritious food to destitute and other poor Children.

From independence until now, the government of India and the States adopted a number of schemes for the promotion and welfare of children. It has established a number of mile stones nationally and internationally to discharge its constitutional and international obligations in promoting the best interests of children . However, due to increasing population, poverty etc. millions of children are not in a position to have a square meal once in a day. Further, the adverse sex ratio of female population is a cause for concern. Apart from the state and a few nongovernmental organizations, the people of the country also need to discharge their bit of services for the augmentation of the children's rights is necessary.

Children, the joy of humankind, the gifts of god, need to be treated with utmost care, love, affection to enjoy their rights as human beings. Whatever schemes are drafted or implemented by the state, without the aid, efforts of the society children rights

cannot be augmented to achieve self-sufficiency. Let the people of the country take a pledge to strive hard to extend their helping hand to one of the vulnerable and most effected populous of the country, namely children, the future generations of the polity in order to wipe out every tear that comes out of the eyes children.

Rights of Socially and Economically Disadvantaged People

Human Rights belong to everyone regardless of any distinction. However, due to socio-cultural and other perspectives, some sections of people face greater vulnerability. This section looks at disadvantaged people, persons belonging to Scheduled Castes/Scheduled Tribes, older persons, persons with disabilities and minority rights.

SC/ ST peoples in the Indian Legal scenario

The hierarchical caste system along with other socio-cultural practices prevailing in India for many centuries has resulted in discrimination and inequality. Despite the abolition of "Untouchability" by article 17 of the Indian Constitution, segregation of persons belonging to Scheduled Castes persists, particularly in some pockets of

rural India, in access to places of worship, housing, hospitals, education, water sources, markets and other public places.

As Per the Government of India 2011 Census, the SC's constitutes around 16.2% population of the country, 166,635,700. As per the Government of India 2011, census, the Scheduled Tribes population comprise 84,326,240 (8.2%) of the total populations. The State with highest proportion of Scheduled Tribes is Mizoram (94.5%), while the lowest proportion being Goa (0.04%).

The following are some important characteristics of STs:-

Geographical isolation - They live in cloister, exclusive remote and in hospitable areas like hills and forests;

Backwardness- Livelihood based on primitive agriculture, low cost closed economy based on low level of technology which leads to their poverty and have a low level of literacy, employment and health.

Distinctive culture, language and religion - About 87 percent of the main workers from STs were engaged in agriculture. The proportion of Scheduled Tribes below the

poverty line is substantially higher than the national average. The estimate of poverty made by Planning Commission for the year 1993-94 shows that 51.92 percent rural and 41.4 percent urban Scheduled Tribes were still living below the poverty line. The Constitution of India incorporates several special provisions for the promotion of educational and economic interests of Scheduled Tribes and their protection from social injustice and all forms of exploitation. "These objectives are sought to be achieved through a strategy known as the Tribal Sub-Plan strategy, which was adopted at the beginning of the Fifth Five Year Plan. The strategy seeks to ensure adequate flow of funds for tribal development form the State Plan allocations, schemes/programmes of Central Ministries/Departments, financial and Developmental Institutions.

The gap in the literacy front may be seen from the fact that as per 2001 census, literacy among ST population was only 47.10% as compared to 64.84% in the general population. It is much more problematic when it comes to tribal women. Only 34.76% of tribal women were literate while the corresponding figure for the general population is 53.67%.

By virtue of the Constitution (Sixty-fifth Amendment) Act, 1990, the Government of India Constituted a National Commission for Scheduled Castes and Schedules Tribes for the promotion and protection of their legal rights. However, in order to specifically cater to needs of schedule casts and scheduled tribes, the government in 2004 bifurcated the Commission and constituted two separate commissions viz., National Commission for Scheduled Castes and the National Commission for Scheduled Tribes respectively.

The framers of the Indian Constitution provided for many provisions to address historical injustices. The Fundamental Rights contained in Part III of the Constitution, consisting of Articles 12 to 35, is considered the 'sole' of the Constitution Accordingly, to augment the rights of these communities the Union and the States of the country enacted a number of legislative enactments.

In addition to Constitutional provisions, a number of legislations were enacted to end discrimination against Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. These include:

- The Protection of Civil Rights (Anti-Untouchability) Act, 1955.

- The Bonded Labour (Abolition) Act, 1976.
- The Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989.

The judiciary has also in a number of cases upheld the validity of various acts of the government for the promotion and protection of the rights of these categories of people and has also directed the state many a times to evolve a number of policy formulations in order to promote, protect and preserve their interests.

Rights of persons with disability in India

The principles of International Law of human rights of disabled persons are reflected in Indian Constitution by way of provisions dealing with Fundamental Rights as well as Articles on Directive Principles of State Policy. The Constitution does not provide for any specific provision dealing with the rights of disabled persons. However, Entry 9 of the State List in the Seventh Schedule of the Constitution refers to – Relief of the disabled and unemployable. Apart from the constitutional provisions, the Government of India enacted specific legislations for the protection and augmentation of the Rights of the Disabled.

In order to ensure its commitment for the development of the rights of disabled, India has signed and ratified the UN Convention and Protocol on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2006. It has assumed all legal obligations without making any reservations. In order to discharge its international and constitutional obligations, the government of India has enacted a number of legislations concerning the rights of differently abled persons. Among the various legislations, the most important of them are:

- The Indian Lunacy Act 1912,
- The Lepers Act, 1899,
- Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act 1995,
- National Trust for Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation and Multiple Disabilities Act 1999,
- Rehabilitation Council of India Act 1992,
- The Mental Health Act 1987.

The judiciary in India, has in a number of cases, also upheld the rights of disabled persons by liberally interpreting

the provisions of the Constitution and the law. It has admonished the discriminatory practices adopted by any section of the society including the state in contravention of the provisions of the various acts.

Conclusion

The brief over view of the rights of various vulnerable groups or disadvantaged people, amply presents the special categories of problems that affect their free exercise of human rights guaranteed both by international and national laws. However, in spite of this, a number of discriminatory practices adopted towards these groups are witnesses in many societies across the world. A cryptic examination provided in this paper certainly imposes a responsibility on each one of us to protect the rights of everyone without any discrimination based on sex, race, language, religion, caste or any other type of discrimination.

At both international and national sphere there are a number of initiatives that have been adopted for the promotion of the rights of the socially and economically disadvantaged people. It is the duty of the majority groups' of the world to desist from such practices and to extend a helping hand

towards the development of the human rights of these people.

Accordingly, we the people of the United Nations have a solemn responsibility to pledge ourselves to promote the human rights education and awareness so that social democracy alone could distance all the evils that exist in the contemporary world, compared to that of political or legal democracy.

The Strict adherence to social democracy would certainly lead us to achieve the path shown by international law of human rights to establish a World free from discrimination of any kind towards the fellow men.

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